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JAMB AND POST-UME SCREENING: THE CHALLENGES OF THE 21ST CENTURY (A POSITIONAL PAPER)

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Abstract

This paper discusses the predictive validity of University Matriculation Examination (UME) used in admitting candidates into Nigerian Universities. The paper notes the concern in recent years about the quality of locally produced Nigerian University graduates and partially attributes the poor quality to admission based on examination scores turned in by the Joint Admissions and Matriculation Board (JAMB). It argues that the Post-UME screening test ~~now~~ used by various Universities for students' intake is an indictment on JAMB as an examination body. The paper highlights the shortcomings of JAMB and concludes that the way forward is to allow both JAMB and Post-JAMB screening examinations to go on but that JAMB should improve on its performance, while the Post-UME screening test should not be allowed to be infected with the same virus that put dent on JAMB creditability as an examination body.

Introduction

Back in 1974, there were seven (7) Federal Universities in the country, each conducting its own concessional examinations and accordingly admitting its students. This system of admission as on the record JAMB online (2006) was characterized by some limitations, including waste of resources in the administration of the concessional examinations, especially on the part of the candidates. The general untidiness in the uncoordinated system of admissions into universities and the attendant problems became a cause for concern to the committee of vice-chancellors (JAMB, 2006). That committee recommended the setting up of two (2) bodies, the central Admissions Board and the Joint Matriculation Board. The Federal military government, however, accepted some of the recommendations of the committee and according to JAMB Decree (1989), set up the Joint Matriculation Board. The legal instrument that gave power to the establishment of the Board was however, according to JAMB Decree (1989), promulgated by the act (No.2 of 1978) of the Federal Military Government on 13th February, 1978. By August, 1988 the Federal Executive Council amended decree No. 2 of 1978 to allow the Board conduct matriculation examinations and place suitably qualified candidates in all Polytechnics and

Colleges of Education (PCE) in the country.

Performance of JAMB

Over the years, the Joint Admissions and Matriculations Board has performed its functions in line with the provision of the Degree that brought it about (JAMB, 2006). The functions of the Board as provided for under section 5 of Decree 33 of 1989 are as follows:

- (i) The general control of the matriculation examinations for admission into all Universities, Polytechnics and Colleges of Education in Nigeria.
- (ii) The appointment of examiners, Moderators, Invigilators, members of the subject panels and committees and other persons with respect to Matriculation Examinations and any other matters incidental thereto or connected therewith.
- (iii) The placement of suitably qualified candidates in the tertiary institutions after having taken into account:
 - a) The vacancies available in such schools;
 - b) The guideline approved for each institution/school;
 - c) The preference expressed or otherwise indicated by the candidates for certain institutions and courses; and
 - d) Such other matters as the Board may be directed by the Hon. Minister to consider or the Board itself may consider appropriate in the circumstances.
- (iv) The collation and dissemination of information on all matters relating to admissions into tertiary institutions or any other matter relevant to the discharge of the functions of the Board.
- (v) The carrying out of such other activities as are necessary or expedient for the full discharge of all or any of the functions conferred on it under or pursuant to this decree.

In carrying out the board's statutory responsibility as set out in the enabling Decree (No. 33 of 1989), the board conducts the UME and the PCE for placement in the respective institutions. Between 1977, and 1986, test papers according to JAMB (2006) were produced abroad but from 1987, the Board's test papers, answer scripts and other materials were printed locally, an exemplary feat. This feat achieved two things. On one hand a greater autonomy was conferred on the Board in the area of preparation and conduct of its examination; but greatly on the other hand, it resulted in a lot of conservation of scarce foreign exchange for the country. Since then, the Board has carried out its responsibilities of conducting examinations and placing applicants creditably until recently when the search for factors responsible for the poor quality of Nigerian graduates has led many into thinking that the problem is solely that of JAMB as a body.

Shortcomings of Jamb as Examining/Admission Body

The genesis of JAMB admission problem can be traced among other things, to the population explosion of the University applicants, which was neither envisaged nor planned. The imbalance between the growth of Universities and students' size created serious set backs in our educational system that have today left a slogan "half-baked graduates" on the lips of many Nigerians.

In some quarters, the poor quality of Nigerian undergraduates is due to the fact that people who present themselves for admission lack required aptitude, ability, interest and motivation for high academic achievement in their chosen courses of study. Nwachuku (1990), furthermore, observed that this set of people lacks personal value for moral integrity, which would have been a sine qua non to the adjudged worthy in character and learning at the end. Nwachuku (2006), therefore, opined that the justification for the introduction of the Post-UME screening must be anchored on its capacity to bridge this gap, by:

- Providing a stronger predictive referent power-base more than JAMB UME, which was somehow shortsighted.
- Exhibiting experts and democratic role referent power-base.
- Ascertaining aptitude, ability, interest and occupational choice implementation relevance.

The Post-UME screening according to Nwachuku (2006), must have the capacity to bring about a demonstration of behavioural compliance with university education, a performance rating of students that is objective and above all, must be leakage and corruption free. The UME she noted, over the years, either lacked all or some of these characteristics or at best intended to reflect them but lacked the proof or capacity to do so. The factors can therefore, be occasionally considered the flaws of UME, which have resulted in the poor quality of Nigerian graduates.

Ubi (2006) noted that a notable flaw of JAMB, which has necessitated a second test, is the unpredictable validity of JAMB scores. It has become increasingly difficult, he noted to place qualified candidates in appropriate courses of their choice because candidates with low ability levels are suspected to out perform those with high ability levels through one form of malpractice or the other. Akpan (1989) described these problems as wholesome unconfirming with Sato's response pattern, a pattern that frowns at scoring a student based on some factors other than what his traits or ability can enable him to. The simple truth is that many candidates, who score high in JAMB and are admitted into Universities on basis of the JAMB scores assigned to their names, do not turn out to be University materials by their actual performance in the Universities' academic programmes. This situation, Isangedighi (1986), Akpan (1995) and Idika (2005), attributed to such malpractices as:

- (a) People writing the examination for others – Impersonation.

(b) Copying, and all forms of malpractices in various centres leading to candidates obtaining grades they do not merit. In line with the popular view that corrupt JAMB officials collect money to change scores for desperate candidates in JAMB record offices, STAN (2001) identified forging of scores by some officials of examining bodies as helping to increase the tendency to cheat among students in examinations. Ubi (2006) affirmed that, the desire to secure admission into Universities has caused candidates to employ all avenues and measures to attain high scores in the UME and this constitutes a serious ill of JAMB as a body. In addition to the ill of impersonation, Akitoye and Shofuyi (cited in Ayang, 2004) noted further that, JAMB permits registration at special centres where special assistance is supposedly rendered to candidates, but now turned to malpractice centres.

From the foregoing, it is obvious that JAMB scores do not tell the truth about the candidates. So admission purely on the basis of JAMB scores has been proven to be deceitful, hence the need for the second test. More so, cheating and other forms of malpractices identified above as characterizing the UME admissions are greatly responsible for the inability of some university graduates to demonstrate the skills they are supposed to possess as indicated on their certificates. Enikuomihin, Badmus and Odor (cited in Idika, 2005) observed that the trend has got to the stage where these Nigerian graduates who cheated their way to examination successes cannot defend their certificates. It is on the basis of these that the proponents of the Post-UME screening have emerged to proffer solution to the admission problems and arrive generally at what should be the near best module for determining the education future of Nigeria.

Emergence of Post-UME Screening as a Strategy And Reform To Address UME Shortcomings

According to Nwachuku (2006), the Post-UME screening emerged as a response treatment to the observed inadequacies of UME-based admissions after many years of practice. Indeed, one of the cardinal reasons for the change in paradigm of UME – body is said to be the astronomical increase in the number of Universities in the country from 2 in 1960 to 12 in 1975; 13 in 1976; 52 in 2003 and now 70, in 2006, which thus called for a harmonized structure to maintain standards in admission. Furthermore, in terms of students' number, Okebukola (2002) noted that, enrolment in university arose from 77, 791 in 1980 to 526, 780 in 2001; and Nwagwu (2003) added that, the phenomenal increase in school enrolment and the resulting crises in education sector, which range from nursery schools to universities created shortage of everything except students. undoubtedly, these increases and crises both at public and private institutions came with consequences of lowered standards and quality especially as this led among others, increase in student-teacher ratio and inability to meet individual needs of students. Education sector has since and shamefacedly embraced public embarrassment from various social influences such as examination leakages and

cheating, certificate racketeering, examination impersonation, monetization of scores, cultism, murder cases and threats on lives of uncompromising university officials. Over the years, the admission practices of JAMB have had to take place in this infected environment and the body has lacked the ability to completely remove itself from the mess of the present society.

Nevertheless, since the establishment of this examining body to the present day, a significant number of entrants into the Nigerian universities had been through a common entrance examination conducted by JAMB and called University Matriculation Examinations (UME). JAMB has continued to play its role in spite of the fact that its real and imaginary weaknesses have continued to attract the attention of all, including the stakeholders that opted for its formation. It is in attempt to address these weaknesses that, the Post-UME screening exercise was born with the aim of critically selecting good quality university candidates from the large JAMB pool; prospective students whose admission scores will be predictive of their performances in the University and an output that will be found worthy in character and learning. As a result, it is expected to be a stronger admission strategy devoid of leakages, malpractices and other corrupt practices. These important requirements according to Ubi and Nwachuku (2006) have not been adequately met by UME.

In an empirical study, Nwachuku (2006) found out that:

- (a) No significant high score relationship exists between JAMB UME and Post-UME screening. That is candidates who scored high in JAMB UME did not score high in Post-UME screening test.
- (b) No significant form of malpractice was experienced in the general conduct of the Post-UME screening. The study thus concluded that all the universities who conducted the screening affirmed that the exercise was definitely a way forward to qualitative admission and invariably qualitative education because of its diagnostic aptitude approach.

Relevance and Limitations of Post-UME Aptitude Testing

There is need for arguments (for and against), which this paper tries to strongly do. The issue is that, should Post-JAMB test be accepted as indictment on JAMB? Is it cheaper and less problematic for individual universities to conduct their own Post-UME test than working on JAMB to make it more reliable examination administering body? After all, individual university staff, both academic and non-academic are usually also involved in the administration of JAMB examinations.

Parents and other segments of the public claimed that the admission policy of Post-UME test is unconstitutional as the decree establishing JAMB is yet to be eradicated or amended (Oloho, 2006). If government were to scrap JAMB, then the universities can return to their original stage where each university conducts and administers its examinations and admits its students with the attendant problems of wastes of resources and unharmonized admissions. Odede (2006) described this situation as "Educational Regionalism".

Akoni (2006) noted that, the Post-UME test is fraught with malpractices and exam error and a forum for JAMB scores profiteering exacerbated by the rich members of the public. He further argued that the Post JAMB test as practiced by some universities, is a cankerworm, a giant dream killer and poverty causative agent, that is against the hopes of aspiring youths. Opalaye (2006), in support, argued that if Federal Government decides to scrap JAMB because of examination malpractices, other examination bodies like WAEC and NECO have to be equally scrapped, because examination fraud takes place at all levels of the educational system including the tertiary institutions. Besides, it is a societal problem in our value system that should be addressed rather than eradicating JAMB. He further argued that if the two admission systems are allowed to stand, it would amount to duplication of roles; a role that would leave candidates stressed up with test-anxiety as they would be made to face two examinations just to secure a single placement.

Oloho (2006) noted that, if the Post -UME test is not immediately abolished, it would be a veritable platform for unscrupulous universities staff to extort money from parents and guardians. For teachers of UME subjects, he further opined that Post -UME screening lessons have earnestly become a huge source of additional income to the detriment of parents and guardians. He concluded that if the post UME screening is accepted, it will encourage ethnicity, favouritism, patronage and other human factors that would be a "cog" in the new admission policy. A national Daily (Independent Advocates, 2006) expressed that one principal factor warranting the apparent need for a second test is the examination malpractice syndrome and maintained that this malpractice is a problem to be fought rather than introduce another device in our educational system. In other words, the main issue according to the daily is the organization of JAMB to see that candidates are able to go in and take examinations without cheating. It therefore recommended some reforms that would detect and stamp out the flaws of JAMB to make the Body function creditably. Indeed this paper believes that patriotic Nigerians are still willing to know more about this, and the big question that will emanate from these is: what is the way out - JAMB or POST-UME test?

Alozie (2006:7), noted that, the body has introduced a lot of guiding factors to counteract the malpractices and other ills:

- a) The "TYPE" system whereby students are made to answer questions by response -set in relation to the course proffered;
- b) Introduction of passports in addition to other profiles for reducing rowdiness in examination halls;
- c) Introduction of the system of on -line registration to effect quick registration of candidates; and
- d) JAMB's current modality of conducting exam, which has proven the Body's zeal to deliver its mission. There is no rationale for the introduction of the much -touted Post-UME test, he concluded.

The relevance of JAMB could be summed up by the fact that it has done much to reduce the phenomenon of ethnicity and tribalism, and so enhanced ethnic and cultural integration among the multi-tribal groups in the country. If admissions are again left to individual universities, there shall be loss in the socio-cultural balance amongst the University Communities. In addition to the above, Okebukola (2002) gave a statistics of past JAMB admission that portrays JAMB to have been able to perform its functions creditably for about 3 decades now. In spite of these arguments for UME, its flaws, if not addressed may still provide the grounds on which the Post -UME screening may not only be overwhelmingly welcomed but embraced as a more qualitative admission strategy.

Implication/Recommendations/Safety Valves and Conclusion

Implication and Conclusion

Much has been done in the area of admission by JAMB. Recent criticisms (argument for the Post-UME screening) do not imply there was nothing positive about the body as JAMB played the role for which it was established creditably well. However, the limitations of JAMB which are not at variance with those of the Nigerian society are what warranted the emergence of Post-UME screening.

The proponent of Post-UME are of the view that the system is an additional means to improve admission practices of JAMB by tightening the loopholes to reposition the university system for a qualitative education right from the point of entry. The position of this paper is that unless the Post-UME operations are vehemently ready to follow the safety valves/recommendations as identified in this paper, then the problem of JAMB would have become the problem of Post-UME screening operators, and subjecting applicants to two different examinations for the same placement would not have been worthwhile. Otherwise Post-UME screening should be allowed to stand, provided that its practices are not reverted to the original status-quo, by which otherwise, JAMB should and be made to sit up.

Recommendations/Safety Valves Against Possible Flaws

The following views are possible conditions under which the Post-UME screening can thrive and stand the test of time:

- An NUC harmonized token Post-UME screening fee (of not more than five hundred Naira (₦500) only) should be charged.
- NUC should provide minimum standards of composition of the Post-UME screening.
- Universities should build to capacity aptitude test writers internally and nationally in collaboration with NUC.
- Statistics and research units of JAMB be made to give yearly updates of the population dynamics of prospective applicants in the country and should work out strategies to absorb changes in this regard bearing in mind that the Board is still the "search engine" for Post-UME screening.

- Provision for periodic workshops as follow-ups and updates and intensive training for integrity of JAMB and Post-UME officials.
- Federal Government's re-orientation of our value system and re-embracing of the ethical revolution concept as contained in decree 2 of 1984; re-emphasis on war against all manner of indiscipline in UME, Post-UME, tertiary institutions and society at large. The Post-UME screening will create a more meaning/public acceptability, if the following negative social influences: ethnicity/statism, leakages, malpractices and certificate racketeering, profiteering of UME and Post-UME scores, general corruption of Post-UME operations, impersonation etc, ^{are} stamped out. The issue of "connection" and god-fatherism", show of wealth and power must not take the Post-UME admission list hostage.

Fund and resource wastage was one of the reasons for formation of the UME Board; a reversal is likely not to be condoned by the masses who may need to pay for UME and Post-UME admission. If these contending issues are not properly addressed, the tendency is that Post-UME may not only lose confidence like JAMB over time, but may be swallowed up by JAMB and leaves our admission saga worse.

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